

Supplementary Appendix: Architectural Overview of SECO-TransP for Evaluating Developer Experience

The architecture of the SECO-TransP framework is structured around a client-server model, designed to integrate data collection from developers and analysis by managers. At the client layer, the system features a Browser Extension that acts as the primary interface for third-party developers to execute scenarios, have their navigation monitored, and submit evaluations. In parallel, there is a Website that encompasses an analytical Dashboard integrated with the server's static assets, allowing administrators to configure evaluation parameters and visualize the collected metrics, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Software architecture of SECO-TransP.¹

The core processing resides in the Server, developed in Python using the Flask framework under the Model-View-Controller (MVC) architectural pattern. This backend exposes a RESTful API responsible for receiving HTTP requests from the client and managing business logic, such as authentication, configuration, and the initiation of an evaluation. This clear separation between client and server via a RESTful API inherently supports scalability, allowing the frontend and backend resources to be scaled independently as the user base grows. Data persistence is

handled through Object-Relational Mapping (ORM) using SQLAlchemy, which establishes structured communication with a MySQL relational database. By utilizing an ORM and a relational database, the framework is well-equipped to manage the storage of large volumes of evaluation data generated by multiple developers.

Finally, the architecture includes integration with the external UX-Tracking system, which utilizes its own browser extension to capture multimodal data and send it to the SECO-TransP server via REST API calls. The data flow is completed when the information stored in MySQL is aggregated by the backend and consumed by the frontend, feeding the portal's dashboard with quantitative and qualitative analyses, such as heatmaps, word clouds, and scenario success indicators.

References

¹Zacarias, R. O. (2025). A Framework for Evaluating Transparency in Software Ecosystem Portals from the Developer Experience Perspective. PhD thesis, Federal University of the State of Rio de Janeiro (UNIRIO), Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.